

A FIRST EDUCATIONAL APPROACH TO CONNECTING KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS

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Abstract:

This article through a search for contemporary research studies, raises a contemporary educational concern in the context of innovative approaches and new pedagogical practices in the field of education sciences. The aim is to make clear an educational philosophy that promotes the development of knowledge and attitudes in relation to the development of skills for a sustainable model of school living.

Keywords: educational action, innovative pedagogical practices, creative school, knowledge and skills

1. Introduction

Contemporary education and training trends, such as Health Education, Health Promotion, Environmental and Sustainability Education etc., as innovative pedagogical interventions through their multifaceted content and their teaching practice, promise a continuing connection between educational theory and practice with socio-cultural reality. Such an approach to educational work can contribute to solving social, economic, ecological and other issues (Hamburg et al., 1982; Smyth, 1995).

This article, through a search for contemporary research studies, raises an educational concern in the context of innovative approaches and new pedagogical practices in the field of education sciences. The aim is to make clear an educational philosophy that promotes the development of knowledge and attitudes in relation to the development of skills for a sustainable model of school living.

2. Modern school and issues

It is recognized that health education and health promotion policies, in combination with educational interventions for positive environmental influences, are increasingly gaining ground. Thus, an upgraded school, ecological and social environment is implemented through a holistic and global approach to knowledge that will stimulate the child's interest and

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creativity. Here, the learning experience is actively lived through collaborative and exploratory learning, with reference to interdisciplinary, that is, the combining of a subject with scientific areas of other subjects and disciplines, thereby making knowledge interdisciplinary (Newell, 2001).

Overall, the above considerations also serve the overriding objective of the modern education system, namely the development of a multi-dimensional human personality through a creative school (Woods & Jeffrey, 1996) of which organization and functioning conditions will meet diverse social needs.

For this reason, learning issues are formulated at cognitive, social and emotional levels as follows (Ernst & Monroe, 2004; Jeffrey & Woods, 2003; Jeffrey & Craft, 2004; Morris, 1956):

- Systematic and reliable information on contemporary social problems, e.g. vandalism and environmental pollution, intimidation, competition and conflict, etc. This can be accomplished through discussion and questioning within the classroom, the issuance of official information and the screening of educational films to arouse interest, etc.
- Awareness and cultivation of reflection on students through experiential techniques on social relations and values, institutions and value systems, as well as on issues of self-awareness of the young person through the dynamics of their relationship with the rest of the social environment, e.g. diversity, friendship, volunteering etc.
- Critical thinking and evaluative ability, that is, capacity building at the spiritual, mental and emotional level, e.g. resolving interpersonal and social problems, etc.
- Social participation through positive and creative forms of behavior, e.g. group sports, musical theater performances, educational walks, painting exhibitions and art creations, etc.

In this context, students develop students' knowledge and attitudes of behavior, developing similar skills in their school performance alongside their social behavior, in a climate of adaptation, communication, socialization, health promotion and living environment, in relation to the rest of the community (Ioannidi, 2006; Ioannidi & Kalokairinou, 2010). In this way, the need for a new education, which will affect cognitive and personal development, by adapting competent pupils and adults, as reflected in the four pillars of Education (Unesco): *“Learning to learn, Learning to act, Learning how to exist, learning to live together”*.

3. Educational process and practices

The educational process itself and the functions of treatment, both at the level of intentional and deliberate effects and also, at the level of interpersonal influences and influences from the wider social, cultural and physical environment, can enhance active learning in the social rules of the young person through the socio-psychological environment of the School (Troman et al., 2007), with a basic orientation:

- the adoption of life values in the educational community, such as respect, love, tolerance, responsibility, cooperation, humility, honesty, freedom, unity, work, peace, etc.,
- creating a moral awareness and critical mindset of students,
- solving problems through understanding social relationships,

- developing positive emotions,
- cultivating creativity in students.

In addition, prevention programs and behavioral trends (Weissberg et al., 1998) can be seen as a pedagogical task within the existing curriculum on the basis of innovative practices that will emphasize alternative programs within the school environment and in collaboration with other social actors (Paraskeva & Papayianni, 2008). Such a psycho-pedagogical framework should be governed by individual pedagogical issues (Krathwohl et al., 1964), such as:

- Providing information to the student through knowledge of his or her individual rights and obligations to others, e.g. school rules, behavioral rules, etc.
- Emphasis on social participation with autonomy and respect for humanitarian values, as well as the natural and anthropogenic environment, e.g. recycling of paper, batteries and other materials, as well as awareness of diversity, violence, etc.
- Practicing personal decision making and prioritizing individual priorities through experiential techniques, e.g. storytelling, role playing, etc.
- Education in social, academic and cultural skills, e.g. educational excursions to historical and archaeological sites, visits to production sites, places of traditional and folklore interest, art exhibitions and protected ecological sites, participation in voluntary activities, etc.
- Seeking for positive and creative experiences in group of school activities, e.g. working in groups to highlight a theme, constructions, art creations, music education, etc.

Therefore, pedagogical processes, with reference to prevention as a new function of treatment, can be made up of a set of educational activities and didactic applications (storytelling, sports and nutrition, traditional dances, solidarity, philanthropy, etc.), as well as alternative programs (for example, health and environmental educational programs, preparedness exercises, etc.), with the aim of fostering social skills, academic learning and ethical values to children. After all, "*knowing the existence*" and "*feeling of coexistence*" is the dual form that plays a central role in school life and in developing a future creative and sustainable social development model (Greenberg et al., 2003).

Generally, it is known that education as a socializing agent and an established primary prevention strategy can provide the necessary conditions for the formation of healthy school and later social behavior (Wallerstein, 1992). The above perception is reinforced by the fact that modern prevention strategies combine young person's information with her education. Consequently, prevention education can be cultivated in a pedagogical environment of experiential learning and can be served as a teaching component for each type and level of educational activity (Ioannidi, 2002). It can be served as a teaching principle that will transcend the learning process and school activity as a whole, with emphasis on Primary, where attitudes and skills are clearly formed and consolidated. Teaching can be interdisciplinary, through dissemination in selected curricula of the curriculum subjects or in the context of educational activities and alternative programs within the community. The ultimate purpose is to foster knowledge, attitudes and skills that promote well-being, human communication and a positive attitude towards the physical and social environment and stimulate the young person's self-awareness in a healthy network of interpersonal and social relationships (Morreale et al., 2007).

4. Epilogue

In conclusion, the overarching concept is the active citizenship (Banks, 1997), which is based on bringing about a creative crisis where the citizen must know to think for the benefit of the whole community, going beyond the mere expression of his or her individual interests. The education of citizens, therefore, must raise the issue of values, and in particular of humanitarian ideas, which will seal the future of the community, which, among other things, gives moral meaning to the pedagogical and professional work of educators.

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Research interests: inclusive education, special needs & disabilities, behavioral problems, learning difficulties, new pedagogical approaches & best practices, social adaptation, teaching methods & interdisciplinary cooperation, early educational intervention, general school, health, education & lifelong learning for all.

References

- Banks J A, 1997. *Educating Citizens in a Multicultural Society*. Multicultural Education Series. N.Y., Teachers College Press.
- Ernst J, Monroe M, 2004. The effects of environment-based education on students' critical thinking skills and disposition toward critical thinking, *Environmental Education Research*, 10: 4, 507-522, DOI: [10.1080/1350462042000291038](https://doi.org/10.1080/1350462042000291038)
- Greenberg M T, Weissberg R P, O'Brien M U, Zins J E, Fredericks L, Resnik H, Elias M J, 2003. Enhancing school-based prevention and youth development through coordinated social, emotional, and academic learning. *American Psychologist*, 58:6-7, 466-474. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.58.6-7.466>
- Hamburg D A, Elliott G R, Parron D L, (eds) 1982. *Health and Behavior: Frontiers of Research in the Biobehavioral Sciences*. Washington, D. C., National Academy Press.
- Ioannidi V, Kalokairinou-Anagnostopoulou A, 2010. *Special Education and Training. Teacher Support - Communication Skills, Trainer Enhancement - Teaching Practices*. An approach for education executives and health professionals. Athens: Beta/medical arts. (in Greek)
- Ioannidi V, 2006. Introduction of innovations in special education. Innovative pedagogical interventions for people with special educational needs: Education for Health and the Environment in children and adolescents with social adaptation difficulties. Series: *Special Pedagogy*, no 6. Athens, Typothyto-G. Dardanos. [in Greek]

- Ioannidi V, 2002. Prevention Education. Publications of the Experimental School of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Vol. 8: "The School in the Third Millennium" (pp. 73-82). Athens: Experimental School of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens.
- Jeffrey B, Woods P, 2003. The creative school. A framework for success, quality and effectiveness. London, N.Y., Routledge Falmer.
- Jeffrey B, Craft A, 2004. Teaching creatively and teaching for creativity: distinctions and relationships. *Educational Studies*, 30:1, 77-87. DOI: [10.1080/0305569032000159750](https://doi.org/10.1080/0305569032000159750)
- Krathwohl D R, Bloom B S, Masia B B, 1964. Taxonomy of Educational Objectives-Handbook II: Affective Domain. New York, Longman.
- Morreale S P, Spitzberg B H, Barge J K, 2007. Human communication. Motivation, Knowledge and Skills. Wadsworth, Thomson.
- Morris A, 1956. Urban Structure and Social Participation. *American Sociological Review*, 21:1, 13-18. Retrieved February 24, 2020, from www.jstor.org/stable/2089334
- Newell W H, 2001. A theory of interdisciplinary studies. *Issues in integrative studies*, 19:1, 1-25.
- Paraskeva F, Papayianni A, 2008. Scientific and pedagogical skills for educational staff. Athens, Pedagogical Institute. [in Greek]
- Smyth President J C, 1995. Environment and Education: a view of a changing scene. *Environmental Education Research*, 1:1, 3-120, DOI: [10.1080/1350462950010101](https://doi.org/10.1080/1350462950010101)
- Troman G, Jeffrey B, Raggl A, 2007. Creativity and performativity policies in primary school cultures. *Journal of Education Policy*, 22:5, 549-572, DOI: [10.1080/02680930701541741](https://doi.org/10.1080/02680930701541741)
- Wallerstein N, 1992. Powerlessness, Empowerment, and Health: Implications for Health Promotion Programs. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 6:3, 197-205. <https://doi.org/10.4278/0890-1171-6.3.197>
- Weissberg R P, Greenberg M T, 1998. School and Community Competence-Enhancement and Prevention Programs. In: Damon W, Sigel I E, Renninger K A (Eds), *Handbook of child psychology: Child psychology in practice* (pp. 877-954). John Wiley & Sons Inc.
- Woods P, Jeffrey B, 1996. Teachable Moments: The art of creative teaching in primary schools. Buckingham, Open University Press.

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